

Anther culture response of indica/basmati heterotic F₁ and F₂ hybrids.

Cultivar/hybrid	Anthers cultured (no.)	Anthers forming (no.)	Calli-regenerating shoots (no.)		
			Albino	Green	Albino/green
<i>Cultivar/breeding line</i>					
Basmati 370 ^a	4200	119 (2.8) ^b	30	6	5.0
HBC5 ^a	4000	130 (3.0)	31	1	31.0
HBC19 ^a	3700	90 (2.4)	8	0	0.0
Pusa Basmati 1 ^a	4700	99 (2.1)	24	1	24.00
HKR239	4700	122 (2.6)	18	3	6.0
HKR86-104	2200	46 (2.1)	0	0	0.0
DM25	1900	65 (3.4)	13	1	13.0
PR106	2300	51 (2.2)	0	0	0.0
IET12012	2400	131 (5.5)	56	25	2.3
<i>F1 hybrid</i>					
HKR86-104/Basmati 370 ^a	3900	101 (2.6)	55	2	27.5
HKR239/Basmati 370 ^a	1600	39 (2.4)	17	1	17.0
DM25/HBC19 ^a	1600	71 (4.4)	54	11	4.9
<i>F2 hybrid</i>					
HKR86-104/Basmati 307 ^a	1600	81 (5.1)	41	7	5.9
PR106/Basmati 307 ^a	1600	57 (3.6)	37	10	3.7
IET2012/HBC5 ^a	3000	171 (5.7)	65	40	1.6
IET12791/HBC5 ^a	1600	67 (4.2)	53	9	5.9
DM25/HBC19 ^a	2600	113 (4.4)	39	6	6.5
HKR86-104/HBC19 ^a	1600	69 (4.3)	26	6	4.3
IET12791/HB19 ^a	1600	62 (3.9)	25	8	3.1
Pusa Basmati 1 ^a /HBC19 ^a	2400	96 (4.0)	22	14	1.6

^aBasmati rice cultivar. Values in parentheses are percentages.

March was of the order of 60-65%. Several of the anther-derived plants had greater number of productive tillers and greater panicle length. On an average, 70% of the plants transferred showed spikelet fertility and set seeds except in case of PR106/Basmati 370 where none of the anther-derived plants produced seeds.

One of the 51 anther-derived plants (designated as AC36) from F₁ DM25/HBC19 hybrid showed exceptionally desirable agronomic characteristics. AC36 had an average of 12.6 productive tillers, a panicle length of 26.2 cm, and 62 filled grains per panicle. This line maintained its Basmati aroma and had a length-breadth ratio of 5.3:1.0 compared with 4.9:1 in HBC19. AC36 had a 1,000 seed weight of 26.4 g compared with 21.1 in HBC19 and 17.7 in DM25. In this generation, however, none of the plants showed the dwarf characteristic of the DM25 parent. ■

Evaluation of rice hybrids in varying environments

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Rice varieties cultivated in coastal areas of India are highly season-specific. Most of them are suitable either for wet (WS) or dry seasons (DS), but a few are suitable for both seasons. Nitrogen fertilization in WS is limited by the problem of lodging caused by frequent rains or storms. Commercial exploitation of heterosis depends on identification of hybrids adapted to variable weather and N levels. Thirty rice hybrids were evaluated in five environments at two N levels in DS, 60 and 120 N (E1, E2) and three in WS, 30, 60, and 120 N (E3, E4, and E5) (see table). They were derived from five CMS lines (IR46830A, IR54752A, IR54754A, IR58025A, and IR62829A) and six restorer lines (WGL3962,

Standard heterosis for grain yield of top 10 heterotic rice hybrids in five environments.^a

Hybrid	Dry season			Wet season	
	E1	E2	E3	E4	E5
IR54752 A/Pratibha	79.6**	74.9**	37.5**	81.7**	46.2**
IR54754 A/Swarna	30.8**	46.8**	58.5**	45.9**	28.7**
IR58025 A/Swarna	67.5**	129.3**	42.9**	112.1**	57.8**
IR58025 A/Vajram	39.9**	77.1**	74.3**	51.1**	49.4**
IR62829 A/Vajram	58.6**	75.5**	50.0**	58.3**	51.9**
IR54754 A/WGL 3962	28.3**	8.7	21.1**	19.2**	34.5**
IR54754 A/Vajram	45.3**	50.2**	48.2**	44.8**	15.3
IR58025 A/WGL 3962	102.2**	32.8**	57.9**	46.8**	15.9
IR62829 A/WGL 3962	81.6**	57.9**	52.1**	32.2**	6.6
IR62829 A/WGL 3962	76.7**	-27.2**	73.4**	69.8**	42.4**
Range of standard heterosis in 30 F ₁ s	-72.2 to 102.2	-78.6 to 129.3	-38.5 to 74.3	-47.2 to 112.1	-65.5 to 57.8

^aE1=60 kg N ha⁻¹, DS; E2=120 kg N ha⁻¹, DS; E3=30 kg N ha⁻¹, WS; E4=60 kg N ha⁻¹, WS; E5=120 kg N ha⁻¹, WS.

Swarna, Vajram, Pratibha, IR36, and IR64). The trial was carried out under an irrigated system at the ARS.

The mean yields of hybrids were generally higher in DS (806 g m⁻²) than in WS (725 g m⁻²). Standard heterosis for yield ranged from -72.2 to 129.3% over IR64 in DS and from -65.5 to 112.1% over Swarna in WS (see table). The hybrids developed using IR58025A as

female parent exhibited a wider range in yield, and standard heterosis ranged from -62.3 to 129.3%. Most of the hybrids performed better in one or the other season whereas some performed better in both seasons.

Five hybrids—IR54752A/Pratibha, IR54754A/Swarna, IR58025A/Swarna, IR58025/Vajram, and IR62829A/Vajram—gave superior performance in

all five environments. Five other hybrids—IR54754A/WGL3962, IR54754A/Vajram, IR58025A/WGL3962, IR62829A/WGL3962, and IR62829A/Swarna—were found superior in four of the five environments studied. Their performance is mainly attributable to heterosis for the number of productive tillers per plant and the number of filled grains per panicle. Only one hybrid, IR62829A/Vajram, which ranked third in grain yield, was stable over the environments with predictable performance ($b_i = 1.57$). Based on linear regression coefficients,

however, the IR58025A/Swarna hybrid with highest yield (1125 g m^{-2}) and high heterosis for yield (85.8) was found to be most suitable for specific environments. The other hybrids, IR58025A/Vajram and IR62829A/Swarna, which had above-average yield (1004 and 857 g m^{-2}) and average response ($b_i = 0.63$ and 2.06) though unpredictable for yield, may also be suitable for specific environments. All four hybrids offer greater scope for commercial exploitation of heterosis in India. ■

IR64, WGL 3962, and IR36 showed good GCA effects for test weight. The line IR54752A was found to be a good combiner for a number of characters, including longer duration and plant height. Among the six restorer lines, Vajram was ranked as a good general combiner for yield, grain number per panicle, spikelet fertility, longer duration, and plant height.

Only the following hybrids showed high SCA effects for one or more characters: IR46830A/WGL 3962 for early flowering; IR54752A/Pratibha for tallness, spikelet fertility, and grain yield; IR46830A/Pratibha for dwarf plant height; IR46830A/Vajram for productive tillers per plant; IR62829A/Pratibha for panicle length; IR46830A/IR36 for grain number; and IR62829A/Pratibha for test weight. Some of these hy-

Combining ability of rice cultivars with IRRI-bred cytoplasmic male sterile lines

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We studied the general combining ability (GCA) of 11 parents (five cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines and six restorer lines) and the specific combining ability (SCA) of 30 crosses in a 5 (line) / 6 (tester) mating design. All the 41 treatments (30 F_{1} s, 5 lines, and 6 testers) were evaluated in a completely randomized block design with three replications during the 1991-92 dry season (DS) under irrigation. Thirty plants for each entry were grown in three 1.5-m row plots with a spacing of 15×15 cm. Five competitive plants were randomly selected from each plot for analysis.

The restorer line WGL 3962 was the best general combiner for grain yield, the CMS line IR46830A was the best general combiner for number of productive tillers per plant, and IR54752A exhibited good GCA for panicle length (Table 1). Three CMS lines (IR58025A, IR62829A, and IR54752A) and three restorer lines (Vajram, IR36, and Swarna) were good combiners for filled grain number per panicle. The lines

IR54752A, IR54754A, WGL3936, Swarna, Vajram, and IR36 were found to be good combiners for spikelet fertility. The line IR54754A and testers

Table 1. General combining ability for grain yield and other characters of 11 parental lines.

Parent	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height	Productive tillers plant ⁻¹	Panicle length	Grains panicle ⁻¹	Test weight fertility	Spikelet fertility	Grain yield
<i>CMS lines</i>								
IR46830 A	-7.95**	-7.80**	1.60**	-0.49**	-24.45**	-0.56*	-9.55**	-126.1**
IR54725 A	4.86**	10.41**	-1.05**	1.03**	8.42**	0.36*	10.43**	83.9**
IR54754 A	1.69**	-0.28	-1.70**	-0.50**	-7.81**	2.57**	3.08*	-81.8**
IR58025 A	4.02**	3.58**	0.69*	0.65**	13.18**	-0.43*	-4.45**	36.0
IR62829 A	-2.98**	-5.92**	0.46*	-0.69**	10.67**	-1.95**	0.50	87.9**
S.E. GCA (L)	0.27	0.81	0.43	0.18	2.75	0.29	1.26	9.9
<i>Restorers</i>								
WGL 3962	-2.03**	-2.52**	0.46	0.27*	1.16	1.93**	5.85**	160.9**
Swarna	1.23**	-0.01	0.50*	-0.51**	7.86**	-1.75**	9.84**	51.8**
Vajram	1.03**	6.72**	1.10	-0.10	35.56**	-1.89**	8.14**	121.6**
Pratibha	3.97**	1.77*	0.04	0.77*	-26.16**	-2.05**	-21.7**	-191.8**
IR36	1.23**	-3.60**	-1.00**	-0.50**	13.91**	1.38**	7.90**	-8.2
IR64	-2.97**	-2.36**	-0.10	0.07	-32.32**	2.38**	-10.01**	-134.3**
S.E. GCA (T)	0.29	0.89	0.47	0.20	3.00	0.33	1.38	10.8

Table 2. SCA effects for grain yield and yield components of elite hybrids (showing >30% standard heterosis).

Hybrids	Standard heterosis	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height	Productive tillers plant ⁻¹	Panicle length	Grains panicle ⁻¹	Test weight	Spikelet fertility	Grain yield
IR58025 A/WGL 3962	89.5	-5.02	0.02	-0.31	0.53	17.55**	-0.72	1.59	209.0**
IR62829 A/WGL 3962	70.0	2.64	-0.35	-1.16	-0.80	-15.30**	-0.11	-3.86	34.4
IR54752 A/Pratibha	68.1	-2.19	6.77**	-0.69	0.08	24.24**	0.48	20.90**	379.2**
IR46830 A/Vajram	67.5	-2.14	3.34	3.00**	-0.42	20.52**	-0.01	13.50**	271.9**
IR62829 A/Swarna	65.5	-0.62	-3.99*	1.27	-0.55	-12.10	-0.03	-8.60**	114.6**
IR58025 A/Swarna	56.9	1.71	2.08	-0.35	0.51	-5.48	2.02	0.83	-88.5**
IR46830 A/IR36	51.3	3.12	2.56	-0.44	0.78	34.33**	0.71	17.47**	298.0**
IR54752 A/IR36	58.6	-3.32	-5.53*	-0.52	0.02	-6.10	0.88	-5.85	71.7**
IR62829 A/Vajram	48.6	-1.76	-3.65	-2.00**	3.67	3.67	0.22	-5.86	-62.8**
IR54752 A/WGL 3962	41.8	3.81	0.05	2.69**	-0.32	-15.92**	-1.11	-11.13**	-140.8**